

A CMS AI to Improve Paper Publishing

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ABSTRACT

This project explores the potential of AI-powered automation in the peer review process for CMS experiment publications at CERN, using the LLaMA 3.1 language model. The research initially employed a fine-tuning approach through Parameter-Efficient Fine-Tuning (PEFT), which, while effective in automating certain aspects such as ensuring consistency with formatting and style guidelines, required significant resources and time. To address these limitations, a prompt engineering approach was later adopted, significantly reducing the time required while improving the accuracy and consistency of reviews. By embedding a summary of CMS internal publication guidelines directly within the prompts, the model was able to perform without additional task-specific training. Both approaches demonstrated the potential for AI to streamline the peer review process, with the prompt engineering method showing particular promise in efficiency. The findings lay a strong foundation for future improvements, including further customization of training processes, dataset expansion, and the development of a graphical user interface (GUI), while also contributing valuable insights into the current capabilities and limitations of AI models in specialized domains.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Scientific paper publishing, especially at CERN and its experiments, follows a rigorous process where each paper must undergo a peer review before it can be made public. At CERN, scientists from over 100 nationalities work together, bringing a variety of writing styles to their papers. This diversity in writing styles makes the peer review process not only time-consuming but also challenging, as reviewers must carefully evaluate each article's style. To alleviate the burden and reduce the time required for peer review, the need for AI assistance in this process has become increasingly important.

Automated peer reviewing tasks would not only involve correcting the entire text but also providing detailed feedback on the changes made. Recent advancements in Natural Language Processing (NLP) and Large Language Models (LLMs) have proven to be more efficient and accurate, making them suitable for handling these time-intensive tasks effectively.

In this study, we present an AI-powered peer reviewer framework that utilizes LLaMA3.1 (LLM from Meta AI) to automate the peer review process for CMS experiment paper publishing. To tackle the computational challenges associated with fine-tuning a LLM, we will also integrate Parameter-Efficient Fine-Tuning (PEFT) methods, such as Low-Rank Adaptation (LoRA).

a. OBJECTIVES

The main objectives of this project are:

- **Streamline the Peer Review Process:** Use LLMs, specifically a fine-tuned Llama 3.1 model, to automate and enhance the peer review process, making it more efficient and consistent.
- **Reduce Time and Effort:** Decrease the time and manual effort required for peer reviewing by automating parts of the process, allowing for quicker turnaround times without sacrificing quality.
- **Optimize Model Training:** Use techniques like PEFT and LoRA to fine-tune the model efficiently, reducing computational resources while maintaining high performance.

2. BACKGROUND

a. AI-ASSITED PEER REVIEW

Peer reviewing is the process of assessing the quality, validity and originality of a paper before is published. It is a crucial but time-consuming process.

The diversity in writing styles and the inconsistencies in following guidelines often slow down the review process, leading to misunderstandings and delays. This is particularly challenging in the context of CMS experiment papers, where precision and clarity are paramount. Therefore, automatizing this process in the most accurate way would be crucial for ensuring that reviews are consistent, efficient, and maintain the high standards required for CMS experiment papers.

b. LARGE LANGUAGE MODELS

Large Language Models (LLMs) are large neural networks trained on enormous datasets, enabling them to perform a wide range of natural language generation tasks with high quality. The main purpose of LLMs is to understand, generate, and interact with human language in a meaningful and contextually relevant way.

LLMs are trained using self-supervised learning, where models learn from unlabeled data by predicting the next word in a sentence. This allows them to leverage vast amounts of raw text. The Transformer architecture, with its self-attention mechanism, enables models to focus on the context of all words in a sentence, making word associations efficiently. This parallel processing capability makes Transformers highly effective for training large-scale language models.

Meta's LLaMA, for instance, focuses on efficient language model training with fewer parameters but strong performance, making it suitable for research and applications where resources are limited. It's used for tasks like text generation, translation, and summarization. Additionally, these models are open-sources, which facilitates broad accessibility and community-driven improvements.

3. PART 1: FINE-TUNING APPROACH

3.1 METHODOLOGY

The process of automating peer review begins by selecting a pre-trained model, which in this case is Llama3.1-8B-Instruct. Since pre-training large language models (LLMs) for peer review can be expensive, we opted to use fine-tuning and prompt engineering as practical and cost-effective approaches to adapt the model for this specific task. The next step involves defining the objective of the automation. I then prepared a dataset consisting of over 1,300 peer-reviewed LaTeX documents and proceeded with fine-tuning and prompt engineering approaches. Following this, the model's performance was evaluated, and based on the results, adjustments and iterations were made as necessary before deploying the model for actual use. In the following sections, I will provide a more detailed explanation of the most important steps.

A. DATA COLLECTION

The data collection process involved web scraping over 1,300 peer-reviewed LaTeX documents from reputable scientific sources. The documents were divided into paragraphs, with each paragraph forming a row in the dataset. During preprocessing, empty rows and incomplete documents were removed to ensure data quality. We ensured compliance with copyright laws by only including open-access documents or those with proper permissions. This clean and ethically sourced dataset was then used to train the model in understanding the structure and content of scientific papers.

B. INITIAL SET UP OF LLAMA3.1

The initial setup of Llama3.1-8B-Instruct involved loading the pre-trained model and tokenizer. The model was sourced from the specified directory, and the tokenizer was configured to handle padding appropriately by assigning the end-of-sequence (EOS) token as the padding token. The dataset was then pre-processed to tokenize the text data, ensuring that it was truncated and padded to a maximum length of 128 tokens. The tokenized input was prepared with corresponding labels to enable effective training for the causal language modelling task.

All experiments were conducted on NVIDIA A100-PCIE-40GB GPU platforms, which provided the necessary computational power to handle the large model and extensive fine-tuning process. This setup ensured that the model was properly initialized and ready for fine-tuning with the given datasets.

C. MODEL FINE-TUNING

One of the approaches I followed to try to achieve an accurate model for peer-review automation was fine-tuning. Fine-tuning refers to the practice of adapting a pre-trained model to a related, but not identical, task or dataset from the one it was originally trained on.

i. PEFTs

To enhance the model's efficiency and accuracy, we employed a PEFT approach, specifically using LoRA. PEFT is important because it allows us to fine-tune large models like Llama3.1-8B-Instruct with fewer trainable parameters. This is crucial due to the model's size and the need to optimize computational resources. LoRA achieves this by introducing low-rank matrices to specific model components, rather than modifying the entire model.

By focusing on key modules such as `q_proj` and `v_proj`, which are integral to the model's attention mechanisms, LoRA allows for targeted adjustments. This focused adaptation helps improve the model's performance on specialized tasks while minimizing computational demands. As a result, we can efficiently enhance the model's capabilities without the need for extensive resources or compromising its core pre-trained knowledge. Key LoRA parameters included:

- **lora_alpha**: Scales the impact of LoRA layers. We set it to 64 to ensure significant adaptation.
- **lora_dropout**: Applies dropout to LoRA layers to prevent overfitting. We used 0.05 for balanced regularization.
- **lora_r**: Defines the rank of low-rank matrices, set to 64 to capture sufficient complexity without excessive resource use.
- **target_modules**: Focused on `q_proj` and `v_proj` modules, crucial for model attention mechanisms.

ii. HYPERPARAMETERS

During the fine-tuning of the Llama3.1-8B-Instruct model, we carefully selected and adjusted several training hyperparameters to optimize model performance. These training arguments significantly impact how effectively the model learns and generalizes from the data. We experimented with various configurations to identify the most effective settings for our specific task.

Key adjustments included setting the token length limit to 2048 tokens and using a batch size of 2. We employed the `adamw_hf` optimizer, which is well-suited for large models and provides effective weight decay regularization. Additionally, we trained the model for various numbers of epochs—5, 10, 15, and 20—to observe how the training and validation loss converged. Through these experiments, we found that training for 20 epochs provided the best results, with the most effective convergence of both training and validation loss.

Each parameter was adjusted iteratively, and different values were tested to find the optimal settings that balanced performance, efficiency, and resource usage. This thorough tuning process ensured that the fine-tuning was both effective and computationally efficient, leading to improved model performance on the peer-review task.

D. PROMPT ENGINEERING

The second approach to enhancing the model for peer-review automation involved prompt engineering, which provides explicit instructions to guide the model's generation process. Unlike fine-tuning, which adjusts the model's weights, prompt engineering leverages the pre-trained model's capabilities by crafting input prompts that effectively direct its behavior.

We employed two primary techniques for prompt engineering:

- **Zero-Shot Learning:** This technique involves designing prompts that enable the model to perform the peer review task without any additional task-specific training. This approach was used to assess the model's ability to generalize its pre-existing knowledge to the new task with no additional examples. An example of a zero-shot prompt template is presented in figure 1.
- **Few-Shot Learning with Input–Output Examples:** In this approach, we provided the model with 4 examples within the prompt to guide its responses more effectively. These examples illustrated the type of feedback or review comments expected, helping the model generate more relevant and accurate peer review outputs. For clarity, the template used for this approach is illustrated in Figure 2.
- **Few-Shot Learning with CMS Writing Guidelines:** In this approach, we incorporated a summary of the CMS writing guidelines into the prompt. These guidelines outline the standards for writing paper publications related to CMS experiments. By providing the model with a condensed version of these guidelines, we aimed to help the model generate peer review comments that align with the expected format and content. We experimented with various numbers of examples to identify the optimal amount that enhanced performance while ensuring the model was not overwhelmed with excessive information. The template used for integrating these guidelines is shown in Figure 3.

Through these experiments, we aimed to determine how different prompting strategies impacted the model's ability to perform peer review tasks. The effectiveness of each approach was evaluated based on the relevance and quality of the generated reviews, as well as the model's ability to generalize from the prompts provided. This exploration of prompt engineering techniques allowed us to leverage the model's capabilities effectively while minimizing the need for extensive task-specific training.

You are an assistant specialized in correcting scientific publications written in LaTeX for the CMS (Compact Muon Solenoid) experiment at CERN. Your primary task is to meticulously review and revise paragraphs for any issues related to readability, clarity, LaTeX formatting, understandability, spelling, and grammar.

Your goal is to ensure that the text is clear, precise, and adheres to the formal writing style typical of CMS scientific papers.

When providing your response, follow this structure:

- Corrected paragraph: If corrections are necessary, provide the revised version of the paragraph.
- Changes made: After the corrected paragraph, list all changes made, explaining each one briefly.
- If no corrections are needed, print the input as is.

Objective: Your overall objective is to assist in the peer review process by ensuring that each publication meets the highest standards of clarity, accuracy, and compliance with CMS guidelines.

Figure 1. Example of Zero-Shot Learning

You are an assistant specialized in correcting scientific publications written in LaTeX for the CMS (Compact Muon Solenoid) experiment at CERN. Your primary task is to meticulously review and revise paragraphs for any issues related to readability, clarity, LaTeX formatting, understandability, spelling, and grammar.

Your goal is to ensure that the text is clear, precise, and adheres to the formal writing style typical of CMS scientific papers. Here are some examples of input and output:

Input:

```
\abstract{
A search is presented for vector-like  $\chi_{PQT}$  and  $\chi_{PQB}$  quark-antiquark pairs produced in proton-proton collisions at a center-of-mass energy of  $\sqrt{s}$ .
Data were collected by the CMS Experiment in 2016, 2017, and 2018, with an integrated luminosity of  $\mathcal{L}$ .
Events with leptonic signatures are selected: one electron or muon, missing transverse energy, and at least three large-radius jets in the single-lepton channel; two electrons or muons with matching electric charge in the same-sign dilepton channel; and three or more electrons or muons in the multilepton channel.
The single-lepton channel utilizes a multilayer neural network and jet identification techniques to discriminate signal events, while the same-sign dilepton and multilepton channels rely on the high-energy signature of the signal to distinguish it from rare standard model backgrounds.
The production of vector-like quark pairs is excluded for  $\chi_{PQT}$  quark masses up to  $m_{\chi_{PQT}}$  and  $\chi_{PQB}$  quark masses up to  $m_{\chi_{PQB}}$  depending on the branching fractions assumed, with maximal sensitivity to decay modes that include multiple top quarks.
These are the strongest limits to date for  $\chi_{PQT}$  production and  $\chi_{PQB}$  quark production with decays to  $lPQlPW$ .
}
```

Output:

Corrected Paragraph:

```
\abstract{
A search is presented for vector-like  $\chi_{PQT}$  and  $\chi_{PQB}$  quark-antiquark pairs produced in proton-proton collisions at a center-of-mass energy of  $\sqrt{s}$ .
Data were collected by the CMS experiment at the CERN LHC in 2016–2018, with an integrated luminosity of  $\mathcal{L}$ .
Events are separated into single-lepton, same-sign charge dilepton, and multilepton channels.
In the analysis of the single-lepton channel a multilayer neural network and jet identification techniques are employed to select signal events, while the same-sign dilepton and multilepton channels rely on the high-energy signature of the signal to distinguish it from standard model backgrounds.
The data are consistent with standard model background predictions, and the production of vector-like quark pairs is excluded at 95% confidence level for  $\chi_{PQT}$  quark masses up to  $m_{\chi_{PQT}}$  and  $\chi_{PQB}$  quark masses up to  $m_{\chi_{PQB}}$ , depending on the branching fractions assumed, with maximal sensitivity to decay modes that include multiple top quarks.
The limits obtained in this search are the strongest limits to date for  $\chi_{PQT}$  production, excluding masses below  $m_{\chi_{PQT}}$  for all decays to third generation quarks, and are the strongest limits to date for  $\chi_{PQB}$  quark decays to  $lPQlPW$ .
}
```

Changes made in Abstract:

Added "at the CERN LHC" after "CMS experiment" to provide additional context.

Changed "in 2016, 2017, and 2018" to "in 2016–2018" for conciseness.

Removed the detailed event selection criteria: "one electron or muon, missing transverse energy, and at least three large-radius jets in the single-lepton channel; two electrons or muons with matching electric charge in the same-sign dilepton channel; and three or more electrons or muons in the multilepton channel" to "Events are separated into single-lepton, same-sign charge dilepton, and multilepton channels."

Changed "discriminate signal events" to "select signal events."

Changed "distinguish it from rare standard model backgrounds" to "distinguish it from standard model backgrounds."

Added "The data are consistent with standard model background predictions" to indicate consistency with the standard model.

Added "at 95% confidence level" to specify the confidence level for the exclusion limits.

Added a specific exclusion limit: "excluding masses below $m_{\chi_{PQT}}$ for all decays to third generation quarks."

Changed "These are the strongest limits to date for χ_{PQT} production and χ_{PQB} quark production with decays to $lPQlPW$," to "The limits obtained in this search are the strongest limits to date for χ_{PQT} production, excluding masses below $m_{\chi_{PQT}}$ for all decays to third generation quarks, and are the strongest limits to date for χ_{PQB} quark decays to $lPQlPW$."

Figure 2. Example of Few-Shot Learning with Input–Output Examples.

You are an assistant specialized in correcting scientific publications written in LaTeX for the CMS (Compact Muon Solenoid) experiment at CERN. Your primary task is to meticulously review and revise paragraphs for any issues related to readability, clarity, LaTeX formatting, understandability, spelling, and grammar.

Your goal is to ensure that the text is clear, precise, and adheres to the formal writing style typical of CMS scientific papers.

When reviewing and correcting the text, please follow these specific guidelines:

- **Readability and Clarity:**
 - Ensure that each paragraph is easy to read and understand. Simplify
 - complex sentences where necessary, while maintaining the scientific integrity and formal tone of the paper.
 - Reorganize or break down sentences that are too long or convoluted, and remove any redundant words or phrases.
- **Grammar and Spelling:**
 - Correct any grammatical errors, including subject-verb agreement, tense consistency, and punctuation.
 - Fix any spelling mistakes and ensure that technical terms and jargon are used correctly.
- **LaTeX Formatting:**
 - Ensure that LaTeX commands are correctly applied, particularly for equations, citations, references, and special symbols.
 - Maintain consistent formatting throughout the document, including section headings, figure and table captions, and references.
 - Verify that all LaTeX code is functional and correctly compiles.
- **Structure and Flow:**
 - Ensure that each paragraph logically follows the previous one, and that the overall structure of the document supports a clear and coherent argument.
 - If necessary, suggest improvements to the flow of ideas or the organization of content.
- **CMS Style Compliance:**
 - Adhere to the specific style guidelines set by CMS, including the use of formal language, proper citation formats, and adherence to the approved structure for scientific publications.
 - Respect the formal tone and style required by CMS, ensuring that all corrections align with these standards.

When providing your response, follow this structure:

- **Corrected paragraph:** If corrections are necessary, provide the revised version of the paragraph.
- **Changes made:** After the corrected paragraph, list all changes made, explaining each one briefly.
- If no corrections are needed, print the input as is.

Objective: Your overall objective is to assist in the peer review process by ensuring that each publication meets the highest standards of clarity, accuracy, and compliance with CMS guidelines.

Figure 3. Example of Few-Shot Learning with CMS Writing Guidelines.

3.2 EXPERIMENTAL DESIGN

To evaluate our model's performance, we designed a comprehensive experimental framework, which involved creating an inference script to process and assess LaTeX documents.

The inference process begins with initializing the pre-trained model and tokenizer, which are loaded from a specified directory. For correcting paragraphs, the script formats the text using a chat template that includes detailed instructions for the model. This formatted input is then passed through the model, which generates corrections based on the provided parameters, such as token limits and sampling methods. The output from the model is decoded to retrieve the corrected text. Additionally, the script processes LaTeX documents by reading and correcting each section, while carefully preserving the document's formatting and handling specific elements like figures and tables. This approach ensures that the LaTeX documents are accurately reviewed and corrected using the model. For a detailed view of the code used for model inference, please refer to the repository <https://gitlab.cern.ch/dsb/proofreading-llm.git>

3.3 RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

Our primary quantitative metrics for evaluating the model's performance were the training loss and validation loss. Although these metrics provide an overview of the model's convergence, they have limitations in reflecting the model's effectiveness in real-world peer review tasks.

- **Training Loss:** This metric decreased steadily throughout the training process, indicating that the model was learning and fitting the training data well.
- **Validation Loss:** We observed a similar downward trend in the validation loss, but with some fluctuations. Lowering the learning rate could potentially smooth these fluctuations and improve validation loss further.

Plots of the training and validation loss are included below in figure to visually illustrate the convergence during the fine-tuning process. These plots serve as a snapshot of one of the most effective training runs where we achieved notable convergence.

Figure 4. Training and Evaluation Loss Over Epochs

Despite the insights provided by these metrics, they do not fully capture the model's performance in more subjective aspects such as writing style and adherence to peer review guidelines. This limitation underscores the importance of complementary evaluation methods.

In addition to quantitative metrics, we employed human evaluation to assess the model's performance, particularly in tasks involving writing style transfer and adherence to specific peer review guidelines. Human evaluators reviewed the model's outputs for several key aspects:

- Consistency with Formatting and Style Guidelines: Writing experts assessed whether the model maintained consistency in formatting and adhered to style guidelines effectively.
- Clarity and Grammar: They also evaluated the clarity and grammatical accuracy of the automated reviews, ensuring that the feedback was coherent and useful.

Human evaluation proved to be a crucial component, especially for evaluating tasks that involve nuanced writing styles and complex scientific content. It offered valuable insights into how well the model could handle these sophisticated aspects of peer review, which were not fully captured by training and validation losses.

3.4 INTERPRETATION OF RESULTS

A. STRENGTHS

The model successfully automated basic grammatical corrections and simple formatting adjustments, which could potentially reduce the workload for human reviewers.

B. LIMITATIONS AND CHALLENGES

Despite fine-tuning, the model's ability to understand and correct scientific content was limited, leading to occasional incorrect or insufficient revisions. The performance of the model showed significant variability depending on the complexity of the input formatting, suggesting that more targeted fine-tuning and additional

training data may be necessary. Additionally, the fine-tuning process took more time than anticipated, highlighting the need for more efficient training strategies and computational resources. These challenges underscore the importance of continued refinement and optimization to enhance the model's reliability and efficiency in handling complex scientific documents.

3.5 CONCLUSION AND FUTURE STEPS

A. IMPLICATIONS OF FINDINGS

The findings of this project demonstrate the potential of AI to assist in the peer review process by automating routine tasks such as grammar correction and basic formatting. However, the limitations observed suggest that the approach we implemented with LLaMA 3.1 is not yet sufficient to fully replace human reviewers, especially for tasks requiring a deep understanding of complex scientific content. Therefore, further investigation into the training and fine-tuning of these models is needed, as their current capabilities show promise but require refinement to fully meet the demands of the peer review process.

B. POTENTIAL APPLICATIONS AT CERN

While the model's current capabilities are limited, there are potential applications in assisting with initial proofreading and ensuring compliance with formatting guidelines. This could serve as a preliminary step before the human review, saving time on lower-level corrections.

C. ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS

The use of AI in peer review raises ethical questions about bias, the potential for AI to overlook nuanced errors, and the reliance on AI in decision-making processes. Ensuring that AI tools are used to assist rather than replace human judgment is crucial in maintaining the integrity of the peer review process.

D. FUTURE DIRECTIONS OF WORK

Future work should focus on improving the model's understanding of scientific content through more targeted training and the incorporation of domain-specific knowledge. Additionally, exploring other fine-tuning methods and expanding the training dataset to include more diverse and complex documents may enhance performance. An important aspect to address is the assessment of LaTeX formatting. Implementing a script to verify whether the LaTeX code is syntactically correct and capable of compiling successfully could significantly improve the model's ability to handle technical formatting issues. There is also a need for ongoing evaluation and refinement of the model's ethical implications, particularly in maintaining the quality and fairness of the peer review process.

4. PART 2: PROMPT ENGINEERING APPROACH

This is the second phase of the project focused on automating the peer review process for CMS experiment publications using AI, specifically the LLaMA 3.1 language model. The initial approach, which involved fine-tuning the model, required extensive resources and time, taking over a week of investigation with mixed results. In contrast, the approach discussed in this report, based on prompt engineering, was completed in less than a week and yielded better outcomes.

Prompt engineering leverages the pre-trained model's capabilities by crafting input prompts that effectively direct its behavior. We employed two main types of prompt engineering: Zero-Shot Learning, which enables the model to perform tasks without additional task-specific training, and Few-Shot Learning, where the model is provided with a few examples to guide its responses. These methods allowed us to harness the model's pre-existing knowledge efficiently, leading to more accurate and consistent peer review outputs.

4.1 METHODOLOGY

The prompt engineering approach was selected as a more efficient alternative to extensive fine-tuning. This method involved crafting specific prompts that leverage the pre-trained capabilities of LLaMA 3.1. We used a summary of the CMS internal publication guidelines as the core prompt, which enabled the model to generate relevant peer review outputs without additional task-specific training. Below you will see an example of the prompt (it needs to be refined by experts) that was used to direct the model's behavior more effectively, ensuring that the outputs aligned with the expected review standards.

```

messages = [
  {"role": "system", "content": """
You are an assistant specializing in correcting scientific publications written in LaTeX for the CMS (Compact Muon Solenoid) experiment at CERN. Your primary task is to meticulously review and revise paragraphs for any issues related to readability, clarity, LaTeX formatting, understandability, spelling, and grammar. Your goal is to ensure that the text is clear, precise, and adheres to the format writing style typical of CMS scientific papers.

You are an assistant specializing in correcting scientific publications written in LaTeX for the CMS (Compact Muon Solenoid) experiment at CERN. Your primary task is to meticulously review and revise paragraphs for any issues related to readability, clarity, LaTeX formatting, understandability, spelling, and grammar. Your goal is to ensure that the text is clear, precise, and adheres to the format writing style typical of CMS scientific papers.

When reviewing and correcting the text, please follow these specific guidelines:

Readability and Clarity:
  Ensure that each paragraph is easy to read and understand. Simplify complex sentences where necessary, while maintaining the scientific integrity and formal tone of the paper.
  Reorganize or break down sentences that are too long or convoluted, and remove any redundant words or phrases.

Grammar and Spelling:
  Correct any grammatical errors, including subject-verb agreement, tense consistency, and punctuation.
  Fix any spelling mistakes and ensure that technical terms and jargon are used correctly.

Language Conventions:
  American English: Ensure that the text uses American English conventions consistently throughout the paper. This includes adjusting spelling, grammar, and punctuation where necessary.
  Serial Comas: Use a comma before the conjunction "and" or "or" in a list of three or more items.
  Hyphenation: Use hyphens to increase clarity where needed, following these guidelines:
    Hyphenate attributive adjectives formed by:
      Noun + participle (e.g., "gas-filled chambers").
      Adjective + participle (e.g., "fine-grained texture").
      "Well", "ill", or "little" + past participle (e.g., "well-known theorem").
      Preposition + noun/adjective (e.g., "next-to-leading-order calculation").
      Temporary compounds with adjectives describing number, dimension, or quality (e.g., "single-photon approximation").
    Do not hyphenate:
      Irregular comparatives or superlatives + participle/noun (e.g., "best known result").
      Foreign phrases (e.g., "a priori solution").
      Adverbs ending in "-ly" + adjective/participle (e.g., "slowly flowing gas").
      Chemical compounds, compounds indicating direction/placement, and commonly used scientific terms.

Common Grammatical Mistakes:
  Articles: Ensure the correct use of "a" versus "an".
  Which vs. That: Distinguish between nonrestrictive (which) and restrictive (that) clauses.
  Avoid sentence-ending prepositions.
  Its vs. It's: Ensure correct usage.
  Associations: Replace "associated to" with "associated with".
  Acronyms: Do not capitalize the first letters of words in a phrase when forming an acronym. For frequently used acronyms in CMS papers, ensure consistent usage.

Term Usage:
  Use "threshold" instead of "cut".
  Replace "errors" with "uncertainties".
  Use "discriminant" instead of "discriminator".
  Avoid physics slang such as "cuts" or "cut tuning". Use "selection criteria" instead.

Special Instructions:
  The term "Higgs boson" should be used consistently when referring to this particle (e.g., "Higgs boson mass" instead of "Higgs mass").
  Avoid the word "fake". Use "misidentified as" instead (e.g., "hadron misidentified as a lepton").
  Use "current" instead of "actual" in formal contexts.

Overall Consistency:
  Ensure that all conventions and terminology are applied consistently throughout the document.

When providing your response, follow this structure:
  Corrected paragraph: If corrections are necessary, provide the revised version of the paragraph.
  Changes made: After the corrected paragraph, list all changes made, explaining each one briefly.
  If no corrections are needed, print the input as is.

Objective: Your overall objective is to assist in the peer review process by ensuring that each publication meets the highest standards of clarity, accuracy, and compliance with CMS guidelines.
  """
}
  
```

Figure 5. Example of a Prompt Used for Peer Review Automation Based on CMS Internal Publication Guidelines

4.3 FUTURE WORK

Building on these findings, future work will explore the following aspects:

- **Expand the Training Dataset:** Future efforts should focus on incorporating a more diverse and complex set of documents into the training dataset. This will enhance the model's ability to handle a broader range of scientific writing styles and content.
- **Improve Model Accuracy:** Exploring additional fine-tuning methods and experimenting with different models may significantly improve accuracy. Incorporating domain-specific knowledge into the training process could also lead to better understanding and correction of scientific content.
- **Adapt the Inference Script for Various LaTeX Structures:** Developing an inference script that can handle diverse LaTeX structures will improve the model's ability to manage technical formatting issues. Implementing a script to verify LaTeX code correctness and compile successfully is a critical next step.
- **Develop a Graphical User Interface (GUI):** To enhance usability, a GUI could be implemented, making the tool more accessible for users who may not be familiar with coding. (Appendix B)

APPENDIX A: Input and Output Example of the Model's Corrections.

ORIGINAL:

The Higgs boson invariant mass (as reconstructed from the di-photon invariant mass, m_{gg}) is the primary experimental observable for this search. Both SM Higgs production processes and the SM Higgs boson from the Tprime are expected to peak on top of a smoothly falling m_{gg} background distribution in the range $100 < m_{\text{gg}} < 180 \text{ GeV}$. The selection criteria on the BDT discriminants for the three different Tprime mass hypothesis ranges have been optimized separately for the leptonic and hadronic categories. The optimization includes the constraint of having a reasonable number of events in the signal sideband regions of m_{gg} , defined by $m_{\text{gg}} < 115 \text{ GeV}$ or $m_{\text{gg}} > 135 \text{ GeV}$. The M_{H} window criterion is synchronized between leptonic and hadronic channels. The complete list of selection criteria and the corresponding number of events in the sideband are provided in Tab.~\ref{tab:sequential_cuts}.

CORRECTED:

Corrected paragraph:

The Higgs boson invariant mass, reconstructed from the di-photon invariant mass (m_{gg}), is the primary experimental observable for this search. Both SM Higgs production processes and the SM Higgs boson from the Tprime are expected to peak on top of a smoothly falling m_{gg} background distribution in the range $100 < m_{\text{gg}} < 180 \text{ GeV}$. The selection criteria on the BDT discriminants for the three different Tprime mass hypothesis ranges have been optimized separately for the leptonic and hadronic categories. The optimization includes the constraint of having a reasonable number of events in the signal sideband regions of m_{gg} , defined by $m_{\text{gg}} < 115 \text{ GeV}$ or $m_{\text{gg}} > 135 \text{ GeV}$. The M_{H} window criterion is synchronized between leptonic and hadronic channels. The complete list of selection criteria and the corresponding number of events in the sideband are provided in Tab.~\ref{tab:sequential_cuts}.

Changes made:

1. Added a comma after "mass" to improve sentence clarity and readability.
2. Changed "from the Tprime " to "from the Tprime " (added a space) to maintain consistent LaTeX formatting.
3. Added a space after "GeV" in the inequality $m_{\text{gg}} < 115 \text{ GeV}$ to improve readability.
4. Added a space after "GeV" in the inequality $m_{\text{gg}} > 135 \text{ GeV}$ to improve readability.
5. Changed the LaTeX command for the inequality from $m_{\text{gg}} < 115 \text{ GeV}$ or $m_{\text{gg}} > 135 \text{ GeV}$ to $m_{\text{gg}} < 115 \text{ GeV}$ or $m_{\text{gg}} > 135 \text{ GeV}$ to maintain consistent formatting and improve readability.

The model focuses on enhancing writing style and content quality rather than prioritizing LaTeX formatting. This approach is intentional to ensure that the primary improvements address the clarity and coherence of the manuscript's content. While the AI contributes to refining the text, it does not fully handle LaTeX formatting, allowing human reviewers to make manual adjustments as necessary. This design choice ensures that the review process remains nuanced and accurate, integrating AI assistance while preserving the critical role of human judgment in managing complex formatting and style issues.

APPENDIX B: IMPLEMENTING A GRAPHICAL USER INTERFACE

This interface enhances the usability of the model by allowing peer reviewers to evaluate and decide on individual AI-recommended changes as they read through a paragraph. By presenting suggested modifications clearly, the tool empowers users to make informed decisions on whether to accept or reject each recommendation. This approach ensures that the AI is used as a supportive tool rather than as the sole authority in the editing process.

Below, you will find a draft of the GUI design that illustrates this concept. The interface highlights suggested changes by underlining the relevant words or sentences. The peer reviewer can then choose to accept or reject each change. Depending on the reviewer's decisions, the final output will be a LaTeX document with the approved corrections. This draft provides a visual representation of how the solution is structured and how it facilitates a collaborative and controlled editing process.

"cut" -> "selection criterion"

The CMS experiment at CERN has recorded a large number of events with a Higgs boson candidate, which is misidentified as a lepton. The events are selected by applying a cut on the transverse energy of the candidate, and then the discriminant is used to separate the signal from the background. The threshold for the discriminant is set to 3.5, and the events are then analyzed to determine the Higgs boson mass. The results show that the Higgs boson mass is consistent with the Standard Model prediction, but with a large uncertainty. The uncertainty is due to the fact that the events are associated to a large number of jets, which makes it difficult to reconstruct the Higgs boson mass.

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Figure 8. Draft Design of the Graphical User Interface (GUI) for Peer Review Automation